

Posters.science - Software Architecture

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A. Overview

Posters.science is a free and open source platform developed by the FAIR Data Innovations Hub. It is intended to make it easier for researchers to share FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and AI-ready scientific posters. This document describes the software architecture of Posters.science; how it will be built, and the rationale behind its design.

B. Overall Architecture

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The core of Posters.science will be a modern full-stack web application framework (e.g., Nuxt 3 built on Vue 3), which will enable a unified web application for both user interface and backend API requests. The entire stack will be developed in a typed language (e.g., TypeScript) for type safety and early bug detection. The framework should support server-side rendering (SSR), which improves security, performance, and search engine indexing.

Posters.science will not host poster files. Instead, posters will remain in established repositories (e.g., Zenodo and Figshare). The platform will act as a registry and index these posters, enrich them with structured metadata, and make them discoverable. The architecture will use:

- A relational database (e.g., PostgreSQL) for poster metadata, user information, and system state
- A search engine (e.g., Meilisearch) for fast, scalable full-text search
- A caching layer (e.g., Redis) for caching and session management
- A database ORM (e.g., Prisma) for typesafe database interactions
- Locally hosted GPU machines for LLM-based extraction and Smart Search
- Python-based web scraping service for repositories without APIs

Deployment will be handled with a deployment tool (e.g., Kamal) on a single Linux server, with CI/CD pipelines (e.g., GitHub Actions) managing automated deployments. Container orchestration (e.g., Docker Compose) will define all services. Documentation will be maintained with a static site generator (e.g., Vitepress).

C. Posters.science Submission Site

The submission service will be integrated into the main platform. Researchers will upload poster PDFs, and the system will automatically extract structured metadata using LLMs. The extracted information will be stored in the database (e.g., PostgreSQL) and indexed in the search engine (e.g., Meilisearch). Posters will be published to repositories (e.g., Zenodo in the first phase, with additional repositories like Figshare supported later) via APIs, with DOIs returned to users.

The submission workflow will consist of the following: (1) upload poster and abstract, (2) review/edit extracted metadata with confidence indicators, (3) choose repository for deposit. The platform will generate a *poster.json* file following the machine-actionable poster JSON schema we will develop as part of this project (based on DataCite with poster-specific extensions). Versioning will be tracked in the database (e.g., PostgreSQL).

C.0. Accepted File Formats

Posters.science tentatively accepts the following file formats for poster uploads:

Primary Formats (Recommended)

- PDF (.pdf) – Most common poster format. Must be single-page.
- PNG (.png) – Lossless image format.
- JPEG (.jpg, .jpeg) – Widely used image format.
- TIFF (.tiff, .tif) – High-quality, print-ready.
- PowerPoint (.pptx) – Must be single-slide.
- SVG (.svg) – Vector format from Figma/Illustrator.

Additional Supported Formats

- PowerPoint Legacy (.ppt) – Older PowerPoint format.
- OpenDocument (.odp) – LibreOffice/OpenOffice presentations.
- Keynote (.key) – Apple Keynote (macOS).
- EPS (.eps) – Encapsulated PostScript vector.
- WebP (.webp) – Modern web image format.
- GIF (.gif) – Limited colors, rare for posters.
- BMP (.bmp) – Uncompressed bitmap.
- HEIF (.heic, .heif) – Apple high-efficiency format.

Page/Slide Requirements

For multi-page formats (PDF, PPTX, PPT, ODP, KEY), only single-page/single-slide documents are accepted as valid posters. Multi-page documents are automatically flagged for review.

Design Tool Exports

If you created your poster in design software like Figma, Adobe Illustrator, or Canva, we recommend exporting as: (1) PDF (preferred) – maintains quality and is widely compatible, (2) SVG – preserves vector quality, or (3) PNG – high-resolution raster fallback.

C.1. Automated Metadata Extraction

The extraction tool will use LLMs to extract structured information from poster PDFs. The pipeline will process PDFs through parsing, layout analysis, OCR fallback, and language detection. Extracted text will pass through our LLM system, which will populate fields according to the machine-actionable poster JSON schema. Each field will receive a confidence score (0-100%) based on format compliance, database validation, and context.

External database integration will validate and enrich metadata through ORCID (author identification), ROR (institution validation), and Crossref Funder Registry (funding validation). For U.S. federal funding, we will cross-reference NIH Reporter and NSF Award Search.

Poster content will be stored in a *contentArray* structure. The LLM will identify major text blocks stored sequentially, with remaining text in an unidentified field. Figure and table captions will be stored in dedicated arrays. This approach accommodates the diverse, unstructured nature of scientific posters better than attempting to force content into predefined sections.

The tool will be containerized (e.g., Docker) with Python 3.10+, exposing RESTful API endpoints. A job queue (e.g., Redis-based) will handle asynchronous processing. Rate limiting will prevent abuse. The architecture will support horizontal scaling through multiple GPU instances.

C.2. Poster Schema Design Rationale

The machine-actionable poster JSON schema will be in adherence to DataCite standards with unique poster metadata needs. Design principles will include: every required field supporting FAIR principles, extensibility through *additionalProperties*, poster-specific fields for gaps in general schemas, JSON format optimized for human readability and AI/ML processing, and interoperability through mapping to repository schemas.

DataCite was selected as the base because it's the industry standard for research output metadata (130M+ DOIs), providing comprehensive bibliographic coverage with strong identifier support (ORCID, ROR, DOI), and includes native funding reference support.

Key poster-specific extensions will include:

- Conference object: captures name, location, dates, acronym, identifiers, and series information (mandatory: name, start/end dates)
- Ethics approvals: array for IRB protocols and ethics certifications
- Domain field: primary research area categorization
- Poster content: *contentArray* structure storing major text blocks (title1-title5) and unidentified text, accommodating unstructured poster layouts
- Figure and table captions: separate arrays with multi-line caption support

The schema will follow semantic versioning, with each version archived on a repository (e.g., Zenodo).

D. Posters.science Discovery Portal

The discovery portal will allow searching through publicly shared posters. A search engine (e.g., Meilisearch) will power search functionality with full-text queries and filtered searches (author, year, conference). When viewing a poster, users will see structured metadata, abstract, and a link to the repository file. A caching layer (e.g., Redis) will cache frequent queries for performance. In the future, the platform will support user-driven feedback for metadata corrections and contributions.

D.1. Smart Search Implementation

Smart Search will enable natural language questions with AI-generated summaries and links to relevant posters. The Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) pipeline will embed user queries, perform vector similarity search against pre-computed poster embeddings in the database, retrieve the top relevant posters (e.g., top 5), and pass them as context to an LLM for response generation.

A possible approach is as follows: An embedding model (e.g., bge-large-en-v1.5, Apache 2.0 license) will be used to cache posters in a high-dimensional embedding space representation (e.g., 1024-dimensional). A vector database extension (e.g., pgvector for PostgreSQL) will store embeddings directly in the database. The poster_embeddings table relies on an index optimized for similarity search (e.g., IVFFlat index for cosine similarity), configured appropriately for the expected poster count (e.g., 100 lists for ~50,000 posters, targeting 10-50ms query performance). Query processing will include entity recognition for conferences/years, medical term expansion with synonyms, and embedding for vector similarity search. Response generation will use RAG with an LLM (e.g., Llama 3.3 70B with 4-bit quantization, deployed via a serving framework such as vLLM) with an appropriate context window (e.g., 8,192 tokens). The vector database will provide capability to give users the top similar posters to a query (e.g., top 5) and will instruct the LLM to synthesize information, cite sources, and respond concisely (e.g., under 300 words).

Evaluation targets are: Precision@5 $\geq 80\%$, semantic similarity score ≥ 0.70 (e.g., using SciBERT), human evaluation $> 3.0/5.0$ (above Acceptable), total latency < 3 seconds. The caching layer (e.g., Redis) caches identical queries for 24 hours. Poster embeddings are pre-computed nightly.

D.2. Overview Page Analytics

The Overview page will provide visualizations of database trends and patterns. Visualizations will use a charting library (e.g., Apache ECharts or D3.js) in Vue 3 components. Data will be served via API endpoints querying database materialized views (e.g., PostgreSQL materialized views, refreshed nightly and cached via the caching layer for 24 hours). The dashboard will include interactive filtering, drill-down capabilities, and export options (PNG, SVG, CSV). Accessibility features will include high contrast mode, keyboard navigation, and screen reader support.

E. Monitoring and Observability

The platform will implement monitoring and observability for system health, performance, and security:

- **Application Monitoring:** A metrics/monitoring solution (e.g., Prometheus or server-native monitoring) tracks backend health (API latency, search indexing, LLM performance, job completion). Alerts route via email or messaging platforms (e.g., Slack). Synthetic monitoring tests end-to-end workflows.
- **Logging:** A centralized logging solution (e.g., Grafana Loki or Azure Log Analytics) centralizes logs including request traces, job results, and errors.
- **Error Tracking:** An error tracking service (e.g., Sentry) monitors real-time errors across the frontend and server-side APIs, capturing exceptions and broken flows.
- **User Analytics:** A privacy-focused analytics tool (e.g., Umami) tracks anonymous usage metrics (searches, metadata corrections, LLM queries).
- **Data Backups:** Nightly database backups (e.g., Postgres backups) export to object storage (e.g., Cloudflare R2), covering metadata, poster.json versions, sessions, and embeddings.
- **Email:** A transactional email service (e.g., Resend) handles transactional emails (verification, password resets, DOI confirmations).

Tools will be introduced incrementally based on deployment scale, starting with health checks and error tracking integration (e.g., Sentry).